

PROBE WG2 “Advanced ABL profiling” - Deliverable 2.1

ABL characterisation

D2.1: Reports, white and review papers on key ABL parameters, their applications, and the end-user requirements.

Project start date	10/2020
Project end date	04/2024

Project title (acronym)	Deliverable 2.1, Product: ABL characterisation
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	with additional contribution from PROBE WG2 members
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1 INTRODUCTION

This report aims at providing a synthesis of key ABL parameters (ABL height, ABL type etc...) for several applications and end-users with the corresponding existing algorithms. For each group of products several references are provided so that the reader can get more details on specific products or accuracy evaluation.

Through all the documents the following acronyms are used:

- ALC: Automatic Lidar Ceilometer
- DL: Doppler Lidar
- MWR: MicroWave Radiometer
- DIAL: Differential Absorption Lidar
- CR, DCR: Cloud Radar, Doppler Cloud Radar
- RL: Raman Lidar
- DeL: Depolarization Lidar
- BL: Backscatter lidar
- RWP: Radar Wind Profilers
- ABL: Atmospheric Boundary Layer

2 METHODS OVERVIEW

To characterise the ABL, numerous advanced algorithms are available, with two main objectives. While most methods provide an estimation of the **height of the ABL** and/or its sublayers, first studies offer additional information on ABL characteristics such as cloud type, atmospheric stability, or the origin of turbulence.

- a) All types of ground-based remote sensing profilers have been used as input to automatic algorithms for **boundary layer height** detection, with most work done on ALC, DL and MWR observations. However, results from different methods can vary substantially¹, simply because they are assessing the ABL sublayer heights based on different atmospheric quantities. Especially during morning growth and evening decay of the mixed layer, the height retrievals may disagree. Comparison studies² indicate that layer heights derived from thermodynamic methods (e.g. analysing MWR profiles) tend to rise ahead of turbulence-based methods (e.g. analysing DL) which again show an earlier growth onset than aerosol-based approaches (e.g. using ALC). Ground-based remote sensing profilers have different capabilities and algorithm uncertainties depend on a variety of atmospheric characteristics which again means the performance of the various retrieval methods can change throughout the diurnal evolution of the ABL³.
- b) Algorithms providing additional information about the state of the ABL are starting to emerge. Given the importance of cloud dynamics for ABL exchange processes, the **cloud type** (convective, stratiform) is assessed in addition to **cloud base height** products (link to cloud and precipitation subgroup). Where temperature (and even humidity) profiles are available from e.g. MWR, the atmospheric stability of the ABL can be determined. DL turbulence observations are now being exploited to characterise the origin of turbulence in the ABL (e.g. surface-driven, shear-driven, clouds-driven)

Given the multitude of available algorithms, fact sheets on recent advanced methods have been collected and will be continuously updated throughout the action. You can find the reference for all the known algorithms available as in March 2021 in Appendix A.

3 PRODUCT OVERVIEW

Products	Mixed layer height (MLH), height of stable layer, ABLH	ABL type (e.g. cloud type, source of turbulence)
Instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ALC (usually applicable to aerosol lidars), - MWR - IRS - Raman lidar - DL 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ALC - MWR - IRS - Raman lidar - DL
Accuracy requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Not yet defined - Expected accuracy indicates ~ 300 m RMSE with respect to reference radiosonde ¹⁸ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Not yet defined
Temporal resolution Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ~ 10 minutes. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ~ 10 minutes.
Assumptions needed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sufficient signal-to-noise ratio - Suitable optical overlap at heights where layers of interest are located - Substantial differences within ABL sublayers must exist when multiple layers have to be detected * 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Convective vs stratiform cloud-topped ABL determination: observed vertical column is assumed to be representative of a larger area, and lidars do not see through to cloud top. - Turbulent source attribution assumes that buoyancy-production (cloud or surface-driven) dominates shear production.
Existing algorithms	<p>As a wide range of algorithms exist, further details are provided in Appendix A: CABAM^{4,5,6}, STRATfinder^{6,7,8}, KABL⁹, ADABL⁹, ACME¹⁰, ABLMAX, BLUSC, ABL characteristics from DL^{11,12,13}, LiRaMi¹⁶</p>	
Application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Air quality research and forecast - Numerical Weather Prediction - Greenhouse gas assessment - Air traffic security 	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Validation of satellite data 	
End users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Air quality agency - National Weather Services - University (Academy) - Airports - Space Agencies 	
Readiness for operation	<p>ALC algorithms being tested for operational applications,</p> <p>MWR and DL algorithms close to operational but used instrumentation is operational</p> <p>Raman lidar: not enough maturity for instrument and algorithm</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - DL: In development, algorithms have been tested on multi-year datasets at multiple sites across Europe and ARM
Expected accuracy	<p>Aerosol-based ABLH algorithms have been reported to agree well with thermodynamic layer heights from 12UTC radiosonde ascends, e.g. found within ± 150 m of each other for 94% of the time¹⁴ or with an RMSE of ~ 160 m⁸. Comparison statistics can be slightly worse when the whole diurnal cycle is considered⁶. Thermodynamic methods applied to MWR profile data show similar or slightly better accuracy than aerosol-based methods (e.g. RMSE ~ 200 m for both¹⁵). Comparison statistics depend highly on timing of radiosondes, methods applied, cloud conditions, and quality control filtering (e.g. screening of rainy periods).</p> <p>Please note that progress needs to be done on the assessment of boundary layer height detection accuracy. This is very challenging due to two major reasons: a) there is no “objective reference” available for comparison and b) results from methods based on different atmospheric quantities can differ due to their physical representation of the atmosphere.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Compared to SYNOP reports, the automatic cloud classification method of CABAM shows good agreement ($> 80\%$), with improved performance during daytime. - ABL classification schemes from MWR and DL data show physically reasonable results, however, given the lack of reference information, evaluation and quantification of accuracy remains challenging and is subject to ongoing research
Temporal resolution	<p>On the order of seconds to minutes (can depend on scanning schedule for MWR and DL)</p>	

Timeliness	On the order of seconds to hours	
Data availability	24/7	
Data format	Mostly netCDF	Instrument .hpl (text) files, or netCDF

* To detect the heights of ABL sublayers, atmospheric quantities within the sublayers must be substantially different so that a layer boundary can be detected. For example, aerosol characteristics in the mixed layer and residual layer above need to be sufficiently different so that a contrast in attenuated backscatter can be observed. Same holds true for turbulence or temperature profile observations.

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Appendix A: Algorithms for the automatic detection of ABL heights and ABL characteristics (status report March 2021)

Contributions from (alphabetical order): Alexander Hieden (ZAMG, Austria), Simone Kotthaus (IPSL, France), Quentin Laffineur (RMI, Belgium), Ewan O'Connor (FMI, Finland), Thomas Rieutord (Météo-France, France), and Iwona S. Stachlewska (university of Warsaw)

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1. ABLH ALGORITHMS

1.1. CABAM

Name of algorithm

CABAM

Key publications

Kotthaus and Grimmond (2018a,b), Kotthaus et al. (2020)

Contact person/ institution(s)

Simone Kotthaus, IPSL (France) and University of Reading (UK)

Output variable/ output information

Mixed layer height (MLH), ABLH (first estimate)

Atmospheric variable analysed

Attenuated backscatter, cloud base height from low-SNR ALC

Algorithm approach

Layer detection based on vertical gradients, layer attribution based on decision tree

Assumptions / corrections

Instrument-related background and near-range artefacts corrected (Kotthaus et al. 2016)

Ancillary data required

no

Evaluation (number of sensors/stations, time periods, reference data)

Applied to multi-year data (CL31, CL51) at multiple sites (10 sites, Paris, London, Beijing, Payerne)

Compared to MLH from DWL; MLH and ABLH from AMDAR temperature profiles; STRATfinder results

Is it already applied in 'operational mode', i.e. in near real-time? Results visible online?

Near real-time implementation at multiple sites: <https://www.lmd.polytechnique.fr/sirta/mld/>

Input data (instrument raw files, ncdf formatted according to some network standard)

E-PROFILE L1

Output data format? (text or ncdf? Compliant with [CF-conventions](#)?)

ncdf, CF compliant

How does the algorithm handle precipitation, clouds/fog?

Internal and external quality control is implemented to remove false layer detection during precipitation. ABLH and MLH can not significantly exceed cloud base height.

Site-specific settings?

Maximum ABLH than may occur, morning growth rate of MLH

Are quality flags provided? If so, how are they determined?

Quality control flags MLH considered physically unreasonable; no flag to indicate uncertainty

Output temporal resolution

Detection performed at native raw resolution (e.g. 30 sec), output averaged to 15 minutes

Algorithm code language

R

License and code availability to others

GNU General Public License v3.0, on Github; implementation not yet very user friendly

Readiness for operation (known remaining weaknesses?)

Algorithm ready for operation. Now being tested in E-PROFILE ABLH testbed.

Remaining issues include:

- Performance clearly depends on quality of input data (e.g. better for CL51 than CL31 input).
- Situations of deep convection (> 2.4km) are not always captured accurately due to noise.
- A specific module is needed to improve detection of residual layer height.
- Interpretation of clouds needs further work: i.e. how to interpret the strong gradient in attenuated backscatter at cloud base of stratiform clouds/fog? Could broken Cumulus clouds form 'within' the ABL?

1.2. STRATFINDER

Name of algorithm

STRATfinder

Key publications

Kotthaus et al. (2020), Haeffelin et al (2012), Poltera et al. (2017)

Contact person/ institution(s)

Simone Kotthaus and Martial Haeffelin, IPSL (France)

Output variable/ output information

Mixed layer height (MLH), ABLH

Atmospheric variable analysed

Attenuated backscatter, cloud base height from high-SNR ALC

Algorithm approach

Graph-theory pathfinding algorithm using field of vertical gradient and variance

Assumptions / corrections

Dynamic overlap model (Hervo et al. 2016)

Ancillary data required

no

Evaluation (number of sensors/stations, time periods, reference data)

Applied to multi-year data (CHM15k) at 2 sites (Paris, Payerne), applied to selected case studies from CHM8k (Munich)

Compared to MLH and ABLH from AMDAR temperature profiles; CABAM results

Is it already applied in 'operational mode', i.e. in near real-time? Results visible online?

Near real-time implementation at 2 sites: <https://www.lmd.polytechnique.fr/sirta/ml/>

Input data (instrument raw files, ncdf formatted according to some network standard)

E-PROFILE L1

Output data format? (text or ncdf? Compliant with [CF-conventions](#)?)

ncdf, CF compliant

How does the algorithm handle precipitation, clouds/fog?

Internal and external quality control is implemented to remove false layer detection during precipitation. ABLH and MLH can not significantly exceed cloud base height.

Site-specific settings?

Maximum ABLH than may occur, maximum nocturnal MLH, morning growth rate of MLH

Are quality flags provided? If so, how are they determined?

Quality control flags MLH considered physically unreasonable; no flag to indicate uncertainty

Output temporal resolution

Native raw resolution (e.g. 30 sec)

Algorithm code language

Matlab. Mcc compiled version now available

License and code availability to others

GNU General Public License v3.0, on Github; also mcc compiled version now available

Readiness for operation (known remaining weaknesses?)

Algorithm ready for operation. Now being tested in E-PROFILE ABLH testbed.

Remaining issues include:

- Weakest point is detection of shallow layers (< 250 m) due to overlap uncertainty.
- Interpretation of clouds needs further work: i.e. how to interpret the strong gradient in attenuated backscatter at cloud base of stratiform clouds/fog? Could broken Cumulus clouds form 'within' the ABL?

1.3. KABL

Name of algorithm

K-means for Atmospheric Boundary Layer (KABL)

Key publications

Rieutord et al., AMT-D (2021)

Contact person/ institution(s)

Thomas Rieutord and Sylvain Aubert, Météo-France

Output variable/ output information

Mixed layer height (MLH)

Atmospheric variable analysed

Range-corrected backscatter

Algorithm approach

Unsupervised classification of measurement points into a “boundary layer” class with K-means

Assumptions / corrections

The mixing layer is in contact with the ground, it has backscatter values significantly different than other layers

Ancillary data required

None

Evaluation (number of sensors/stations, time periods, reference data)

Applied on MiniMPL lidar (SigmaSpace) on two sites (Brest and Trappes, France) over 2 years (2017-2018). Compared to ADABL and the manufacturer’s algorithm.

Is it already applied in ‘operational mode’, i.e. in near real-time? Results visible online?

No

Input data (instrument raw files, ncdf formatted according to some network standard)

NetCDF issued from raw2l1 (E-PROFILE L1) one file per day

Output data format? (text or ncdf? Compliant with [CF-conventions](#)?)

Add a field “blh” in the NetCDF input file. Probably not CF-compliant but easy to change

How does the algorithm handle precipitation, clouds/fog?

Precipitations and fog discarded from the evaluation. For cloud, an additional class is created in the profile. When no other layer is present between the ground and the cloud, the MLH is the cloud base height.

Site-specific settings?

No

Are quality flags provided? If so, how are they determined?

No. Some quality scores are calculated on the classification, but their use as quality flag is still to be tested.

Output temporal resolution

Same as the input (one estimation per profile)

Algorithm code language

Python 3

License and code availability to others

CeCILL (French equivalent of GNU/GPL), available on Github :
<https://github.com/ThomasRieutord/kabl>

Readiness for operation (known remaining weaknesses?)

- Continuity of the estimation in time is not very good (e.g. oscillations between surface layer and cloud). It can be corrected thanks to a post-processing, for example, with a moving average or by imposing a maximum BLH growth rate (Poltera et al., 2017).
- Operation on various device was not tested

1.4. ADABL

Name of algorithm

AdaBoost for Atmospheric Boundary Layer (ADABL)

Key publications

Rieutord et al., AMT-D (2021)

Contact person/ institution(s)

Thomas Rieutord and Sylvain Aubert, Météo-France

Output variable/ output information

Mixed layer height (MLH)

Atmospheric variable analysed

Range-corrected backscatter in co-polarised and cross-polarised channel

Algorithm approach

Supervised classification of measurement points into a “boundary layer” class with boosting

Assumptions / corrections

The mixing layer is characterized by values similar to those used to train the boosting algorithm

Ancillary data required

None

Evaluation (number of sensors/stations, time periods, reference data)

Applied on MiniMPL lidar (SigmaSpace) on two sites (Brest and Trappes, France) over 2 years (2017-2018). Compared to ADABL and the manufacturer’s algorithm.

Is it already applied in ‘operational mode’, i.e. in near real-time? Results visible online?

No

Input data (instrument raw files, ncdf formatted according to some network standard)

NetCDF issued from raw2I1 (E-PROFILE L1) one file per day

Output data format? (text or ncdf? Compliant with [CF-conventions](#)?)

Add a field "blh" in the NetCDF input file. Probably not CF-compliant but easy to change

How does the algorithm handle precipitation, clouds/fog?

It recognize it from the training set and identify the MLH accordingly

Site-specific settings?

Will work better when trained on data from the same site

Are quality flags provided? If so, how are they determined?

No. Some quality scores are calculated on the classification, but their use as quality flag is still to be tested.

Output temporal resolution

Same as the input (one estimation per profile)

Algorithm code language

Python 3

License and code availability to others

CeCILL (French equivalent of GNU/GPL), available on Github :
<https://github.com/ThomasRieutord/kabl>

Readiness for operation (known remaining weaknesses?)

- The training is the main limitation : it is done with human-expertised MLH time series, it must be a large set (several days), with various conditions
- Operations on various device was not tested and it is expected to be highly device-dependent

1.5. ACME

Name of algorithm

ACME (Austrian CeiloMeter Evaluation)

Key publications

Lotteraner and Piringner (2016)

Contact person/ institution(s)

Hieden Alexander, ZAMG (Austria)

Output variable/ output information

Aerosol Layer Heights (ALH), Mixing Height (MH)

Atmospheric variable analysed

ALH: Attenuated backscatter, cloud base height

MH: lowest ALH, lowest cloud base height, wind speed

Algorithm approach

ALH: Derivative analyses of the backscatter intensity

MH: Using the lowest ALH; using the lowest cloud base height, if the lowest cloud is stratiform; outlier filtering; filling gaps by linear interpolation; height limitation of nocturnal values depending on wind speed; smoothing by moving average

Assumptions / corrections

ALH: outlier filtering, cluster merging

MH: Aerosols and polluted air emitted near the ground disperse vertically primarily up to the lowest aerosol-layer height. Limitation of nocturnal values depending on wind speed

Ancillary data required

ALH: no

MH: wind speed, site-specific parameters

Evaluation (number of sensors/stations, time periods, reference data)

Multi-year evaluations of ALH for 30 sites, selected case studies (ALH and MH)

Is it already applied in 'operational mode', i.e. in near real-time? Results visible online?

ALH: Near real time operation of ALH for 27 sites. Online results – internal access only.

MH: not yet

Input data (instrument raw files, ncd format according to some network standard)

ALH: Raw device output

MH: lowest ALH, lowest cloud layer height, wind speed, site-specific parameters

Output data format? (text or ncd? Compliant with [CF-conventions](#)?)

ALH: Text & ncd

MH: Text

How does the algorithm handle precipitation, clouds/fog?

ALH: Precipitation and clouds are filtered out by a functional match of the backscattering amplitude against a sigmoid function of the height.

Site-specific settings?

ALH: No

MH: Yes (real horizon heightening and geographical coordinates for day-night separation)

Are quality flags provided? If so, how are they determined?

No

Output temporal resolution

ALH: Selectable

MH: 5 minutes

Algorithm code language

ALH: Python 3+

MH: Fortran90

License and code availability to others

No

Readiness for operation (known remaining weaknesses?)

- Cloud and precipitation filtering needs further improvement
- Uncertainty rises with higher spatial and temporal resolutions
- Mixing Height not yet operational, but foreseen in 2021

1.6. ABLOMAX

Name of algorithm

ABLOMAX

Key publications

Not yet

Contact person/ institution(s)

Quentin Laffineur, RMI (Belgium)

Output variable/ output information

Mixed layer height (MLH), quality flag

Atmospheric variable analysed

Attenuated backscatter, cloud base height (CBH)

Algorithm approach

Calculation of the occurrence for each level where there is a local extremum in the domain of the vertical gradient and the variance in a given time interval.

Assumptions / corrections

The level where the occurrence is highest near the ground is considered as the mixing layer height (MLH)

Ancillary data required

no

Evaluation (number of sensors/stations, time periods, reference data)

Applied on 4 CL51 in Belgium from September 2020 up to now. Evaluation on CL51 data of June 2019. A long-term study is still needed.

Is it already applied in 'operational mode', i.e. in near real-time? Results visible online?

Near real-time on 4 sites (CL51)

Visible on this link: <https://cloud.meteo.be/s/xMGGbjeD2Qz3bwN> (PWD: ABLOMAX2021)

Input data (instrument raw files, ncdf formatted according to some network standard)

Vaisala data file format

Output data format? (text or ncdf? Compliant with [CF-conventions](#)?)

text

How does the algorithm handle precipitation, clouds/fog?

ABLOMAX continuously outputs a MLH value except under fog or heavy precipitation conditions. MLH can not exceed CBH.

Site-specific settings?

No

Are quality flags provided? If so, how are they determined?

Quality control flags based on the backscatter values at the top and bottom of the mixing layer level.

Output temporal resolution

10 min

Algorithm code language

Python 2.7

License and code availability to others

No

Readiness for operation (known remaining weaknesses?)

Algorithm ready for operation.

Remaining issues include:

Situations of deep convection and low backscatter signal are not always captured accurately.

2. ABL CHARACTERISATION

2.1. CABAM

Name of algorithm

CABAM

Key publications

Kotthaus and Grimmond (2018a,b), Kotthaus et al. (2020)

Contact person/ institution(s)

Simone Kotthaus, IPSL (France) and University of Reading (UK)

Output variable/ output information

Dominant ABL cloud type (cloud free, cumulus, stratiform, MLH remaining below stratiform cloud base) for nocturnal (between sunset and sunrise) and daytime periods

Atmospheric variable analysed

Attenuated backscatter, cloud base height from low-SNR ALC

Algorithm approach

Combining cloud base height temporal variability with MLH products

Assumptions / corrections

Instrument-related background and near-range artefacts corrected (Kotthaus et al. 2016)

Ancillary data required

no

Evaluation (number of sensors/stations, time periods, reference data)

Applied to multi-year data (CL31) at multiple sites (10 sites, Paris, London, Beijing, Payerne)

Compared to SYNOP reports for London

Is it already applied in 'operational mode', i.e. in near real-time? Results visible online?

Not yet implemented operationally

Input data (instrument raw files, ncdf formatted according to some network standard)

E-PROFILE L1

Output data format? (text or ncdf? Compliant with [CF-conventions](#)?)

Not yet standardised

How does the algorithm handle precipitation, clouds/fog?

Precipitation flags from MLH detection algorithm

Site-specific settings?

Maximum ABLH than may occur, morning growth rate of MLH

Are quality flags provided? If so, how are they determined?

no flag to indicate uncertainty

Output temporal resolution

Detection performed on 15 minute data, output aggregates nocturnal and daily conditions

Algorithm code language

R

License and code availability to others

To be included into CABAM GNU General Public License v3.0 on Github

Readiness for operation (known remaining weaknesses?)

- Further testing and evaluation required

2.2. BLUSC

Name of algorithm

Boundary Layer Unsupervised and Supervised Classification

Key publications

In preparation: Rieutord et al. (2021)

Contact person/ institution(s)

Thomas Rieutord, Météo-France

Output variable/ output information

Pixel-based boundary layer classification

Atmospheric variable analysed

Absolute temperature from MWR

Range-corrected backscatter from ceilometer

Algorithm approach

Two approaches are proposed:

- unsupervised classification with hierarchical clustering --classes are unidentified, and
- supervised classification (several algorithms) --classes are identified but these algorithms need training.

Assumptions / corrections

There exist several types of boundary layer and they are marked by significantly different values in the temperature and backscatter measurements.

Ancillary data required

None

Evaluation (number of sensors/stations, time periods, reference data)

Constructed on a set of 10 days during Passy-2015 campaign

Is it already applied in 'operational mode', i.e. in near real-time? Results visible online?

No, current status is only the proof of concept

Input data (instrument raw files, ncdf formatted according to some network standard)

NetCDF CF-compliant files

Output data format? (text or ncdf? Compliant with [CF-conventions](#)?)

Add three fields in the input netCDF :

- rawlabels (integer identifying the BL type for each pixel),

- label_identification (dict associating label to BL type short name), and
- label_long_names (dict associating BL type short and long name).

How does the algorithm handle precipitation, clouds/fog?

They are identified as a such with a dedicated class

Site-specific settings?

No for unsupervised classification, probably yes for supervised

Are quality flags provided? If so, how are they determined?

No

Output temporal resolution

Chosen by the user. Recommendations are to use the resolution of the coarsest instrument

Algorithm code language

Python 3

License and code availability to others

CeCILL (French equivalent of GNU/GPL), available on Github :
<https://github.com/ThomasRieutord/bl-classification>

Readiness for operation (known remaining weaknesses?)

- Preliminary work
- Run on a broader data set, with various conditions, geography and instruments
- Define a relevant evaluation metric and compare to existing BL classification

2.3. BOUNDARY LAYER CLASSIFICATION FROM DOPPLER LIDAR

Name of algorithm

Boundary layer classification from Doppler lidar (Halo lidar toolbox)

Key publications

Manninen et al. (2018), Vakkari et al. (2019), Pentikäinen et al. (2020)

Contact person/ institution(s)

Ewan O'Connor, FMI (Finland)

Output variable/ output information

Presence of turbulence, source of turbulence, and whether the region is in contact with the surface.

Atmospheric variable analysed

Vertical Doppler velocity moments, attenuated backscatter, vertical profile of horizontal winds

Algorithm approach

Combines turbulent parameters (epsilon and skewness) with winds (horizontal and shear), cloud and precipitation identification, to determine presence of turbulence, source of turbulence, and whether the region is in contact with the surface.

Assumptions / corrections

Requires reliable background, telescope focus corrections, calibration.

Ancillary data required

None, but inclusion of atmospheric stability or surface heat flux aids interpretation

Evaluation (number of sensors/stations, time periods, reference data)

Applied to about 10 sites in Europe, and at 5 ARM sites

Is it already applied in 'operational mode', i.e. in near real-time? Results visible online?

Being tested in NRT for a few sites, these results are not yet visible online. Previous datasets are available online

Input data (instrument raw files, ncdf formatted according to some network standard)

Instrument .hpl (text) files, or netCDF

Output data format? (text or ncdf? Compliant with [CF-conventions](#)?)

netCDF compliant with CF conventions where possible

How does the algorithm handle precipitation, clouds/fog?

Precipitation and cloud are handled as part of the classification process

Site-specific settings?

In principle no, but SNR at some sites/instruments is very low hampering calculation of turbulent properties. Correction for background and telescope focus function key to algorithm performance

Are quality flags provided? If so, how are they determined?

Uncertainties of interim products are calculated. Plan is to combine all uncertainties into probability classes.

Output temporal resolution

Usual temporal resolution is 3 minutes, but can be averaged over longer periods at sites with low SNR.

Algorithm code language

Currently Matlab, but due to be ported to Python.

License and code availability to others

Available on github

Readiness for operation (known remaining weaknesses?)

Better diagnosis of convective vs shear driven turbulence. Dealing with site variability in SNR. Improving setup for new stations/instruments. Better diagnosis of light precipitation, and gravity-wave contribution.

2.4. LIRAM_i

Name of algorithm

Lidar, Radar, Microwave Radiometer Synergy Algorithm

Key publications

Wang et al. (2020)

Contact person/ institution(s)

Iwona Stachlewska, University of Warsaw

Output variable/ output information

Spatio-temporal discrimination of polarization and molecular, aerosol and cloud scattering

Atmospheric variable analysed

Lidar: Scattering ratio, Colour ratio, quasi-Particle backscattering ratio

Could Radar: reflectivity, Doppler velocity

Microwave radiometer: temperature, relative humidity

Algorithm approach

Instrument synergy based data products for boundary layer aerosols and clouds classification using threshold approach.

Assumptions / corrections

The different atmospheric constituents can be discerned using sets of thresholds applied on simultaneous observations done with 3 different remote-sensing instruments.

Ancillary data required

None

Evaluation (number of sensors/stations, time periods, reference data)

Algorithm was demonstrated for 24 hours of observations on 10 June 2019 in Rzecin, Poland during POLIMOS field campaign. Classification publication for the entire campaign (~3 months co-located data) is in review.

Is it already applied in 'operational mode', i.e. in near real-time? Results visible online?

No NRT evaluation for this moment. Data evaluation within a week from the observation date is possible. Script run at University of Warsaw only.

Input data (instrument raw files, ncdf formatted according to some network standard)

NetCDF CF-compliant files, ASCII files

Output data format? (text or ncdf? Compliant with [CF-conventions](#)?)

NetCDF CF-compliant files, ASCII files

How does the algorithm handle precipitation, clouds/fog?

They are identified as a such with a dedicated class

Site-specific settings?

No

Are quality flags provided? If so, how are they determined?

No

Output temporal resolution

Chosen by the user. Recommendations provided in algorithm documentation.

Algorithm code language

Matlab

License and code availability to others

On request by contacting University of Warsaw

Readiness for operation (known remaining weaknesses?)

Run on a broader data set, with various conditions, geography, and site type (urban, rural).

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